

Microwave-assisted copper azide alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) reaction using D-glucose as a better alternative reductant[†]

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Abstract : D-Glucose has been established as a reducing agent for the copper azide alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) reactions. Efficacy of this new reductant has been established against various phenyl acetylenes (14 examples) and aryl azides (16 examples). All reactions proceeded smoothly and 1,2,3-triazolyl derivatives (30 examples) were obtained in moderate to excellent yields (68–96%).

Keywords : Benzyloxy propyne, phenyl azide, glucose, copper sulphate, 1,2,3-triazole.

Introduction

An exothermic fusion to form triazole ring via azide alkyne cycloaddition (AAC) reactions has enjoyed its legacy in drug discovery, bioconjugation and materials science¹ since the first synthesis of 1,2,3-triazole (*v*-triazole) from phenyl azide and acetylene dicarboxylic ester was reported by Michael² in 1893, followed by Holder³ and Raschig⁴. Tolerance of various azides and alkynes for the formation of *v*-triazoles was excellent, however these cycloaddition reactions showed very low regioselectivity and yielded a mixture of 1,4- and 1,5-regioisomers⁵. Sustmann proposed the difference between HOMO-LUMO energy level of both azides and alkynes to be responsible for the lack of regioselectivity⁶. The difference between HOMO-LUMO energy levels of both azides and alkynes are very close in magnitude and hence both dipole-HOMO and dipole-LUMO interact simultaneously and subsequently yield a mixture of regioisomers.

The improvement of the poor regioselectivity of dipolar cycloaddition involving azides and alkynes was an attractive and challenging target till 2002, when Fokin and Sharpless proposed a historic Cu^I-catalyzed protocol for the regioselective cycloaddition reactions⁷. Earlier, even several groups had described different protocol to control this 1,4- versus 1,5-regioselectivity issue; none

of them succeeded in generating a method of wide applicability. Different catalysts were proposed for different substrates⁸ and these catalysts are not readily available.

Nevertheless, Cu^I-catalyzed protocol for the synthesis of 1,4-regioisomers described by Fokin and Sharpless is mild and convenient. Subsequently, they also observed that *in situ* reduction of Cu^{II} salt by sodium ascorbate to be a better choice as compared to direct use of Cu^I source^{1g}. Although, sodium ascorbate has proven to be an excellent reductant for the synthesis of a wide spectrum of 1,4-triazole products, it suffers from several disadvantages in addition to being hazardous in the case of ingestion, skin contact, eye contact and in the case of inhalation.

From the view point of economical and environmental consideration, it is highly desirable to search less expensive and less toxic reagents for chemical transformations. In this regard D-glucose as reductant would be a good candidate for CuAAC reaction because of its relatively low cost and practically no toxicity. The reduction of Cu^{II} by glucose was first reported by Fehling in 1849⁹ and subsequently by Benedict in 1908¹⁰. They had successfully generated Cu^I from CuSO₄ in the presence of sodium citrate and sodium carbonate. Thereafter, several reports and reviews have been published till date¹¹. Re-

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

cently, Younan and co-workers have developed Cu⁰ nano tube by reducing Cu^{II} in the presence of glucose¹². Very recently, Guchhait and his group have reported the *in situ* generation of Cu^I from Cu^{II} by using glucose as reductant for aldehyde, alkyne and amine (A³) coupling¹³. Role of glucose as reductant is historically known and well documented in literature; however there is no evidence for the microwave-assisted CuAAC reaction where glucose is used as a reductant. Herein, we report an environment-friendly, microwave-aided methodology in which Cu^I-Cu^{II} system is generated *in situ* from CuSO₄ in the presence of glucose as reductant in CuAAC reaction (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1,2,3-triazole.

Results and discussion

At the outset, we chose benzyloxy propyne (1) and phenyl azide (2) as model substrates. When a mixture of benzyloxy propyne (1, 1.0 mmol) and phenyl azide (2, 1.2 mmol) was refluxed in the presence of readily available CuSO₄·5H₂O and D-glucose as reductant for 14 h in ethanol, reaction proceeded smoothly with the formation of the desired product 3 in 52% yield (Table 1, entry 1). Further screening of various solvents was executed and the results are summarized in Table 1. This screening revealed that those organic solvents which dissolve/partially dissolve CuSO₄ yield the desired products (Table 1, entries 1–5) whereas non-dissolving solvents do not lead to the formation of the desired product (Table 1, entries 6–9) but resulted in complete recovery of both the starting materials even after 30 h of refluxing. We found that the solubility of CuSO₄ in solvent system is crucial in this reaction. Subsequently, water was added to these organic solvents to increase the solubility of CuSO₄ in the solvent mixture (different ratios were tried but the best yield was observed in 2 : 1 ratio) and reactions were performed under identical conditions. As expected, all solvents worked well in this biphasic solvent system (Table 1, entries 11–15) except MeCN : H₂O mixture (Table 1, entry 10). The best result was obtained in 2 : 1 mixture of

Table 1. Optimization of solvent system for CuAAC reactions^a

Entry	Solvents	Time (h ^b /min ^c)	Yield (%) ^d
1	EtOH	(14 h/ 15 min)	52/62
2	H ₂ O	(22 h/ 10 min)	34/45
3	MeOH	(30 h/ 15 min)	32/41
4	1,4-Dioxan	(20 h/ 15 min)	28/36
5	DMF	(22 h/ 15 min)	20/28
6	Toluene	(30 h/ 10 min)	Nr
7	MeCN	(22 h/ 15 min)	Nr
8	DCM	(16 h/ 10 min)	Nr
9	THF	(18 h/ 10 min)	Nr
10	MeCN : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(20 h/ 20 min)	Nr
11	DCM : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(13 h/ 10 min)	45/54
12	Toluene : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(28 h/ 15 min)	27/41
13	1,4-Dioxan : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(28 h/ 15 min)	32/40
14	DMF : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(35 h/ 15 min)	21/32
15	THF : H ₂ O (2 : 1)	(16 h/ 10 min)	48/69

Reaction condition : ^a1.0 mmol of benzyloxy propyne, 1.2 mmol of phenyl azide, 0.2 equiv. of CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.4 equiv. of D-glucose were reacted in the appropriate solvent for time mentioned in above table, ^bunder conventional condition, ^cunder microwave condition, ^disolated yield, Nr = no reaction; recovered both the starting materials.

THF and H₂O (Table 1, entry 15). In order to improve the yield and reduce the time when we performed this reaction under microwave irradiation, significant improvement in the yield and time was observed (Table 1) and

the best yield (69%) was observed when acetylene **1** and phenyl azide **2** were irradiated in microwave for 10 min (Table 1, entry 15) in 2 : 1 mixture of THF and H₂O.

For CuAAC reaction, the nature of Cu^I salt is very crucial because of its dual action¹⁴. In CuAAC, Cu^I functions both as a π and σ -electrophilic Lewis acid. Keeping these facts in mind, several Cu^I sources were examined and results are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Optimization of Cu-sources in CuAAC reactions^a

Entry	Cu-Sources	Reductant	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	-	15	Nr
2	CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	Glucose	10	69
3	Cu(OAc) ₂ ·H ₂ O	-	10	Nr
4	Cu(OAc) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Glucose	15	42
5	CuI	-	15	26
6	CuI	Glucose	15	35
7	CuBr	-	10	30
8	CuBr	Glucose	15	32

Reaction condition : ^a1.0 mmol of benzyloxy propyne, 1.2 mmol of phenyl azide, 0.2 equiv. of Cu-sources, 0.4 equiv. of D-glucose in THF : H₂O (2 : 1) were irradiated in microwave for optimum time mentioned in the above table, ^bisolated yield, Nr = no reaction; recovered both the starting materials.

Amongst the screened Cu sources, CuSO₄·5H₂O was found to be most effective in generating Cu^I in the presence of glucose as reductant and yielded desired product **3** in 69% yield (Table 2, entry 2). Reaction did not proceed in the absence of reductant and both starting materials were completely recovered at the end of the reaction. On the other hand, different sources like Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O, CuI and CuBr gave lower yields in the presence of glucose. Moreover, in the absence of the reductant, significantly lower yields were obtained in case of CuI, CuBr (Table 2, entries 5 and 6). However, no product formation was observed when CuSO₄·5H₂O and Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O were used as Cu source (Table 2, entries 1 and 3).

To improve the yields further, literature-guided screening of nitrogen-based ligand was performed for this CuAAC reaction in the presence of glucose (Table 3).

Previous reports have evidenced the tremendous improvement in the percentage yield of the desired product by adding nitrogen-based ligand in the presence of an apolar solvent¹⁸. In CuAAC reaction, nitrogen-based ligands strongly bind Cu^I and prevent the formation of unreactive polymeric complexes A₁ (Scheme 2)¹⁸. This allows the azide to access the coordination sphere of σ -acetylide Cu centre and also these ligands act as a base, which helps in promoting the reaction efficiently by forming Cu^I-Cu^{II} system. Apolar solvents demote the aggregation of Cu-species and hence promote the ligand exchange, which leads to the detrimental effect on the rate and outcome of reaction.

Table 3. Optimization of bases/ligands in copper azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) reactions^a

Entry	Bases/Ligands	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	DIPEA	10	87
2	TEA	15	69
3	Pyridine	15	80
4	Sodium carbonate	15	40

Reaction condition : ^a1.0 mmol of benzyloxy propyne, 1.2 mmol of phenyl azide, 0.2 equiv. of CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.4 equiv. of D-glucose in THF : H₂O (2 : 1) as a solvent under microwave irradiation with the mentioned base (2 equiv.) and the time, ^bisolated yield.

Therefore several commercially available N-containing ligands were explored based on this hypothesis. Interestingly, all tried ligands were effective and reactions proceeded smoothly (Table 3). N,N-Diisopropylethylamine or Hünig's base (DIPEA) appeared to be the best ligand for this reaction. Under similar condition, DIPEA yielded desired compound in 87% yield, (Table 3, entry 1), whereas other ligands such as triethylamine (TEA) and pyridine yielded 69% and 80% of the desired compound, respectively (Table 3, entries 2 and 3). Nevertheless, only simple base like Na₂CO₃ gave much inferior yield (Table 3, entry 4), which is consistent with the hypothesis.

Under optimal reaction conditions, 1 mmol of the substituted benzyloxy propyne, 1.1 mmol of phenyl azide,

0.2 equiv. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.4 equiv. of D-glucose and 2 mmol of DIPEA were added to a 2 : 1 mixture of THF and water taken in a 10 mL sealed glass vial. After 10–15 min of microwave irradiation, the triazole product was isolated and different alkynes were investigated to evaluate the generality of the reaction. The results are summarized in Table 4. The substrates bearing either an electron-donating group (Table 4, entry 2) or electron-withdrawing group (Table 4, entries 3–15) on the phenyl ring were well tolerated under optimized reaction conditions. In general, good to excellent yields were obtained for the desired cyclised products. Moreover, this protocol appeared to be insensitive to the electronic properties of the functional group present in the phenyl ring.

Table-4 (contd.)

Table 4. Generalization of CuAAC reactions with different aromatic alkynes

Entry	1 and 4-16	Compd.	R	Product	3 and 17-29	Yield (%)
1	1 and 3	H			87	
2	4 and 17	3-OMe		81		
3	5 and 18	3-F		68		
4	6 and 19	3-Cl		90		
5	7 and 20	3-Br		72		
6	8 and 21	4-F		77		
7	9 and 22	4-Cl		87		

8	10 and 23	2,3,4,5,6-F		93	
9	11 and 24	2-F		72	
10	12 and 25	4-CHO		95	
11	13 and 26	2-COCH ₃		94	
12	14 and 27	3-COCH ₃		87	
13	15 and 28	4-COCH ₃		90	
14	16 and 29	4-NO ₂		78	

In the next step, we also applied this protocol to various substituted phenyl azides. The desired products were obtained in good to excellent yields (Table 5); the effect of the electronic property of the functional group present on the phenyl ring was not observed.

On the basis of our experimental observations and literature, we believe that initially CuSO_4 forms aqua complex ion **2** which subsequently reacts with base such as DIPEA to give complex **3**¹⁵. Complex **3** further reacts with glucose and gives chelate like complex **4**¹⁶, which is in tune with the copper complex formed in Benedict and Fehling's test^{9,10}. This complex **4** finally through electron transfer mechanism^{11(a)} produces gluconic acid and cupric oxide [Cu_2O , Cu^{I}] (Scheme 2), which subsequently reacts with alkyne to form π -complex **6** which on hydrogen elimination gives copper acetylides complex **7**. This copper acetylide reacts instantly with azide in a [3+2]

Table 5. Copper azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC) reactions with different aromatic azides

Entry	Compd.	Azide	Product	Yield (%)
1	30 and 46	$m = 1$, $R = \text{H}$		88
2	31 and 47	$m = 1$, $R = 4\text{-NO}_2$		85
3	32 and 48	$m = 0$, $R = 4\text{-CH}_3$		96
4	33 and 49	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-CH}_3$		92
5	34 and 50	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-CH}_3$		80
6	35 and 51	$m = 0$, $R = 4\text{-OCH}_3$		74
7	36 and 52	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-OCH}_3$		88
8	37 and 53	$m = 0$, $R = 2\text{-OCH}_3$		94

Table-5 (contd.)

9	38 and 54	$m = 0$, $R = 4\text{-F}$		82
10	39 and 55	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-F}$		83
11	40 and 56	$m = 0$, $R = 2\text{-F}$		73
12	41 and 57	$m = 0$, $R = 4\text{-Cl}$		92
13	42 and 58	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-Cl}$		73
14	43 and 59	$m = 0$, $R = 2\text{-Cl}$		88
15	44 and 60	$m = 0$, $R = 4\text{-Br}$		88
16	45 and 61	$m = 0$, $R = 3\text{-Br}$		80

cycloaddition manner to give intermediate **10**. The final product 1,2,3-triazole (**11**) is obtained from the intermediate **10** by the elimination of copper(I), as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Catalytic cycle of the Cu-catalysed reaction.

Conclusions

In summary, we have developed a new reducing agent for CuAAC reactions. It was compatible with a variety of phenyl acetylenes and phenyl azides and delivered regioselective 1,2,3-triazolyl derivatives in moderate to excellent yields. It would be a better alternative to sodium ascorbate for reducing CuSO_4 for this reaction; Cu^I was readily generated from CuSO_4 by glucose. Further exploration of this economical and environment-friendly reductant is currently going on in our laboratory and would be reported in due course.

Experimental

General information :

Analytical TLCs were performed on Merck silica gel 60_{F254} plates. All liquid column chromatographic separations were performed on Biotage Flash Column Chromatography. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 2000 FT-IR spectrometer at Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi. Synthesis of 1,2,3-triazoles was car-

ried out in a CEM Discover microwave instrument. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra (in CDCl_3) were recorded on a JEOL ECX-400P NMR at 400 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively at USIC, University of Delhi; TMS was used as internal standard. The NMR spectra were processed by JEOL DeltaTM NMR data processing software, the chemical shift values are on a δ scale and coupling constants (J) are in Hz. Abbreviations used are : s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), dd (double doublet) and m (multiplet). The high-resolution mass spectral data were obtained using a JEOL JMS-SX-102A spectrometer at Institut für Chemie und Biochemie, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany. Melting points were recorded on a Büchi M-560 melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. All the chemicals and reagents like phenol, aniline, benzyl derivatives and propargyl alcohol were purchased from commercial sources and used as received unless otherwise indicated. Literature methods were used to synthesize 4-(phenoxy)methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole¹⁷ (**3**), 4-((3-methoxyphenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole¹⁸ (**17**), 4-((2-fluorophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole¹⁷ (**24**), 4-((4-fluorophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole¹⁹ (**21**), 4-((4-nitrophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole¹⁹ (**29**), 4-((4-chlorophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole²⁰ (**22**), 1-(4-((1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methoxy)phenyl)ethanone²⁰ (**28**), 1-benzyl-4-(phenoxy)methyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazole²¹ (**46**). The spectroscopic features of the known compounds are in good agreement with those reported in the literatures.

*General procedure for the synthesis of prop-2-yn-1-yloxybenzenes 1 and 4-16*²² :

A mixture of appropriate phenol (1 mmol) and propargyl bromide (1.2 mmol) in DMF was stirred with K_2CO_3 at room temperature for 20–24 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC [ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1 : 4)]. After completion of reaction, it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 mL). The combined ethyl acetate layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated under reduced pressure and used directly in the next step without any further purification.

*General procedure for the synthesis of azidobenzenes 2 and 34-46*²³ :

A mixture of appropriate aniline (1 mmol) in 17% HCl was stirred at 0 °C, aqueous sodium nitrite (1.5

mmol) was added dropwise and stirring continued at 0 °C. After 15 min, aqueous sodium azide (1.5 mmol) was added dropwise at 0 °C and contents stirred for 3–4 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC [ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1 : 5)]. After completion of reaction, it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 mL). The combined ethyl acetate layer was dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated under reduced pressure and used directly in the next step without any further purification.

*General procedure for the synthesis of azidomethylbenzenes 32 and 33*²⁴ :

A mixture of appropriate benzyl bromide (1 mmol) and sodium azide (1.5 mmol) in DMF as a solvent was stirred at room temperature for 6–8 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC [DCM/hexane (1 : 5)]. After completion of reaction, it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 mL). The combined ethyl acetate layer was dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated under reduced pressure and used directly in the next step without any further purification.

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-(phenoxy)methyl-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole and its derivatives 17-29 and 46-61 :

A mixture of appropriate alkyne (1 mmol), appropriate azide (1.2 mmol), CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.2 equiv.), D-glucose (0.4 equiv.) and *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine [DIPEA (2 mmol)] were taken in a 2 : 1 mixture of THF and water (1.5 mL) in a 10 mL glass vial equipped with a small magnetic stirring bar, and the vial was tightly sealed with a Teflon crimp top. The mixture was then irradiated in microwave for 10–15 min at 70 °C and 100 W irradiation power. The progress of the reaction was monitored on TLC [ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1 : 3)]. After completion of reaction, it was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 30 mL). The combined ethyl acetate layer was dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated under reduced pressure and finally purified by column chromatography to yield the desired products **17-29** and **46-61**.

Characterization of the products :

4-((3-Fluorophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole (18) :

It was obtained as a yellow solid having m.p. 92.0–94.0 °C in 68% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3141, 1597, 1138, 756; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.07 (1H, s), 7.74 (2H, d, *J* 8.08 Hz), 7.54–7.50 (2H, m),

7.46–7.43 (1H, m), 7.27–7.22 (1H, m), 6.82–6.69 (3H, m), 5.27 (2H, s) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 164.7, 159.3, 144.3, 136.8, 130.3, 129.7, 128.8, 121.0, 120.5, 110.3, 108.2, 102.7, 62.0 ppm; HRMS calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂FN₃ONa : 292.0862; found [M+Na]⁺ : 292.0857.

4-((3-Chlorophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole (19) :

It was obtained as a light brown solid having m.p. 101.0–103.0 °C in 90% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3063, 1595, 1225, 760; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.08 (1H, s), 7.76 (2H, d, *J* 8.08 Hz), 7.56–7.53 (2H, m), 7.48–7.45 (1H, m), 7.28–7.22 (1H, m), 7.05–6.93 (3H, m), 5.29 (2H, s) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 158.7, 135.5, 134.9, 130.3, 129.7, 128.9, 121.5, 121.0, 120.5, 115.3, 113.0, 62.0 ppm; HRMS calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂ClN₃ONa : 308.0567; found [M+Na]⁺ : 308.0561.

4-((3-Bromophenoxy)methyl)-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole (20) :

It was obtained as a brown solid having m.p. 99.0–101.0 °C in 72% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3096, 1590, 1222, 770; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.05 (1H, s), 7.73 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 7.53–7.41 (3H, m), 7.17–7.09 (3H, m), 6.96–6.93 (1H, dd *J* 1.44, 8.04 Hz), 5.26 (2H, s) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 158.8, 136.8, 130.6, 129.7, 128.9, 124.4, 122.8, 120.9, 120.5, 118.2, 113.4, 62.0 ppm; HRMS calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂BrN₃ONa : 352.0061; found [M+Na]⁺ : 352.0064.

4-(Perfluorophenoxy)methyl-1-phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole (23) :

It was obtained as a white solid having m.p. 100.0–102.0 °C in 93% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3133, 1514, 994; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.14 (1H, s), 7.75–7.73 (2H, m), 7.57–7.53 (2H, m), 7.49–7.47 (1H, m), 5.41 (2H, s) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 143.3, 136.8, 129.5, 129.1, 121.6, 120.6, 67.8 ppm; HRMS calcd. for C₁₅H₈F₅N₃ONa : 364.0485; found [M+Na]⁺ : 364.0489.

4-((1-Phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methoxy)benzaldehyde (25) :

It was obtained as a white solid having m.p. 99.0–101.0 °C in 95% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 2924, 1690 (C=O), 1164, 756; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) :

δ 9.87 (1H, s), 8.07 (1H, s), 7.84 (2H, d, J 8.80 Hz), 7.72 (2H, d, J 8.04 Hz), 7.56–7.49 (3H, m), 7.13 (2H, d, J 8.76 Hz), 5.35 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 190.7, 163.0, 143.9, 136.8, 132.0, 129.8, 129.0, 121.1, 120.6, 115.0, 62.0 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 302.0905; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 302.0909.

1-(2-((1-Phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methoxy)phenyl)ethanone (26) :

It was obtained as a brown solid having m.p. 97.0–99.0 °C in 94% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3157, 1656 (C=O), 1291, 759; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.07 (1H, s), 7.73–7.69 (3H, m), 7.51–7.43 (4H, m), 7.15 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.02 (1H, m), 5.38 (2H, s), 2.58 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 199.7, 157.1, 136.7, 133.6, 130.3, 129.7, 128.9, 121.2, 121.5, 112.8, 62.3, 31.8 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 316.1062; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 316.1065.

1-(3-((1-Phenyl-1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methoxy)phenyl)ethanone (27) :

It was obtained as a light brown solid having m.p. 90.0–92.0 °C in 87% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2924, 1676 (C=O), 1271, 765; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.08 (1H, s), 7.74 (2H, d, J 8.08 Hz), 7.62–7.39 (6H, m), 7.25–7.22 (1H, m), 5.33 (2H, s), 2.59 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 197.8, 158.3, 142.5, 138.4, 136.8, 129.7, 128.9, 121.6, 121.1, 120.5, 119.9, 113.6, 61.9, 26.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 316.1062; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 316.1066.

1-(4-Nitrobenzyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (47) :

It was obtained as a yellow solid having m.p. 89.0–91.0 °C in 85% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3100, 1603, 1350, 755; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.20 (2H, d, J 6.56 Hz), 7.63 (1H, s), 7.40 (2H, d, J 8.04 Hz), 7.30 (2H, d, J 8.08 Hz), 6.99–6.94 (3H, m), 5.64 (2H, s), 5.21 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 157.9, 147.9, 141.4, 129.5, 128.5, 124.2, 122.9, 121.3, 114.6, 61.8, 53.1 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Na}$: 333.0964; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 333.0959.

4-(Phenoxyethyl)-1-(p-tolyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (48) :

It was obtained as a white solid having m.p. 125.0–127.0 °C in 96% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2922, 1490, 1232, 826; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.02

(1H, s), 7.61 (2H, d J 8.04 Hz), 7.32–7.29 (4H, m), 7.03–6.97 (3H, m), 5.29 (2H, s), 2.42 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.1, 138.9, 134.6, 130.2, 129.5, 121.2, 120.4, 114.6, 61.9, 21.0 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{ONa}$: 288.1113; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 288.1109.

4-(Phenoxyethyl)-1-(m-tolyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (49) :

It was obtained as a light yellow solid having m.p. 58.0–60.0 °C in 92% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3148, 1597, 1492, 1230, 751; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.06 (1H, s), 7.59 (1H, s), 7.53 (1H, d, J 8.08 Hz), 7.43–7.39 (1H, m), 7.35–7.31 (2H, m), 7.27 (1H, s), 7.05–6.99 (3H, m), 5.32 (2H, s), 2.46 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 142.5, 139.9, 136.8, 129.5, 129.4, 121.2, 121.1, 120.9, 117.5, 114.6, 61.8, 21.3 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{ONa}$: 288.1113; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 288.1116.

4-(Phenoxyethyl)-1-(o-tolyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (50) :

It was obtained as a dark brown semi solid having 80% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2927, 1592, 1489, 1236, 754; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.75 (1H, s), 7.35–7.25 (6H, m), 6.98–6.91 (3H, m), 5.26 (1H, s), 2.15 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 144.0, 136.2, 133.6, 131.4, 129.9, 129.5, 126.8, 125.9, 124.2, 121.3, 120.1, 115.3, 114.7, 61.8, 17.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{ONa}$: 288.1113; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 288.1115.

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (51) :

It was obtained as a light brown solid having m.p. 90.0–92.0 °C in 74% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2937, 1600, 1239, 753; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.19 (1H, s), 7.79–7.76 (1H, dd, J 8.04, 1.46 Hz), 7.44–7.40 (1H, m), 7.33–7.29 (2H, t), 7.10–6.98 (5H, m), 5.30 (2H, s), 3.87 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 157.3, 151.2, 130.1, 129.2, 125.2, 120.8, 114.5, 111.9, 61.2, 55.6 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 204.1062; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 304.1067.

1-(3-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (52) :

It was obtained as a brown semi solid in 88% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2937, 1598, 1495, 1237, 754; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.04 (1H, s), 7.40–7.23

(6H, m), 7.02–6.95 (3H, m), 5.29 (2H, s), 3.87 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 160.5, 158.0, 137.8, 130.4, 129.5, 121.3, 115.4, 114.7, 114.6, 112.3, 107.9, 106.3; 61.7, 55.5 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 304.1062; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 304.1064.

1-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (53) :

It was obtained as a dark brown semi solid in 94% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2937, 1600, 1507, 1240, 753; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.16 (1H, s), 7.77–7.75 (1H, dd, J 1.46, 8.05 Hz), 7.45–7.38 (1H, m) 7.31–7.27 (2H, m), 7.10–6.94 (4H, m), 6.77–6.71 (1H, m), 5.28 (2H, s), 3.85 (3H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.1, 150.9, 143.3, 130.1, 129.4, 125.3, 125.0, 121.1, 119.2, 114.9, 112.1, 110.2, 61.8, 55.3 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Na}$: 304.1062; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 304.1069.

1-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (54) :

It was obtained as a brown solid having m.p. 98.0–100.0 °C in 82% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3142, 1518, 1231, 846; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.01 (1H, s), 7.72–7.69 (2H, m), 7.33–7.29 (2H, m), 7.24–7.19 (2H, m), 7.03–6.97 (3H, m), 5.30 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 145.1, 133.2, 129.5, 122.6, 122.5, 121.3, 121.0, 116.8, 116.6, 114.6, 61.8 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{FN}_3\text{ONa}$: 292.0862; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 292.0869.

1-(3-Fluorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (55) :

It was obtained as a dark brown semi solid having 83% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3141, 1603, 1482, 1230, 748; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.04 (1H, s), 7.53–7.47 (3H, m), 7.32–7.28 (2H, m), 7.15–7.11 (1H, m), 7.01–6.96 (3H, m), 5.28 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 164.4, 161.7, 158.0, 145.3, 137.3, 131.2, 129.6, 121.4, 120.7, 115.9, 114.6, 108.4, 61.8 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{FN}_3\text{ONa}$: 292.0862; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 292.0865.

1-(2-Fluorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (56) :

It was obtained as a light yellow solid having m.p. 81.5–83.5 °C in 73% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3166, 1599, 1241, 753; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.07

(1H, d, J 2.52 Hz), 7.88–7.84 (1H, m), 7.35–7.32 (1H, m), 7.24–7.17 (4H, m), 6.95–6.88 (3H, m), 5.21 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.2, 154.5, 152.0, 144.5, 130.3, 129.5, 125.2, 124.8, 123.9, 121.2, 117.0, 115.3, 114.6, 61.6 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{FN}_3\text{ONa}$: 292.0862; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 292.0861.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (57) :

It was obtained as a dark brown solid having m.p. 134.0–136.0 °C in 92% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2973, 1600, 1238, 759; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.70 (1H, s), 7.68 (2H, d, J 8.79 Hz), 7.49 (2H, d, J 8.79 Hz), 7.31–7.27 (2H, m), 7.01–6.95 (3H, m), 5.29 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 135.3, 134.6, 129.9, 129.5, 121.7, 121.3, 114.6, 61.8 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_3\text{ONa}$: 308.0567; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 308.0561.

1-(3-Chlorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (58) :

It was obtained as a dark brown solid having m.p. 63.0–65.0 °C in 73% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3094, 1597, 1489, 1251, 751; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.03 (1H, s), 7.76–7.75 (1H, m), 7.62–7.59 (1H, m), 7.45–7.37 (2H, m), 7.30–7.26 (2H, m), 7.00–6.94 (3H, m), 5.27 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 157.9, 137.6, 135.5, 130.8, 129.5, 128.8, 121.3, 120.8, 118.4, 114.6, 61.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_3\text{ONa}$: 308.0567; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 308.0569.

1-(2-Chlorophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (59) :

It was obtained as a dark brown semi solid having 88% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2928, 1591, 1482, 1237, 751; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.04 (1H, s), 7.61–7.54 (2H, m), 7.45–7.42 (2H, m), 7.31–7.27 (2H, m), 7.02–6.95 (3H, m), 5.30 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 134.4, 130.8, 130.6, 129.5, 128.5, 127.8, 127.7, 124.8, 121.2, 114.7, 61.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_3\text{ONa}$: 308.0567; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 308.0568.

1-(4-Bromophenyl)-4-(phenoxyethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (60) :

It was obtained as a light yellow solid having m.p. 143.5–145.0 °C in 88% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3103, 1498, 1230, 752; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ

8.04 (1H, s), 7.66–7.61 (4H, m), 7.33–7.29 (2H, m), 7.02–6.97 (3H, m), 5.29 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 158.0, 145.3, 135.8, 132.8, 129.5, 122.5, 121.9, 121.3, 120.6, 114.6, 61.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_3\text{ONa}$: 352.0061; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 352.0058.

1-(3-Bromophenyl)-4-(phenoxymethyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole (61) :

It was obtained as a light yellow solid having m.p. 91.0–93.0 °C in 80% yield; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 2916, 1585, 1252, 751; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 8.03 (1H, s), 7.92 (1H, d, J 1.83 Hz), 7.68–7.65 (1H, dd, J 2.20, 8.05 Hz), 7.55 (1H, d, J 8.05 Hz), 7.39–7.34 (1H, m), 7.31–7.27 (2H, m), 7.00–6.95 (3H, m), 5.27 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 157.9, 145.3, 137.7, 131.8, 131.0, 129.5, 123.5, 123.2, 121.3, 120.7, 118.9, 114.6, 61.7 ppm; HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{BrN}_3\text{ONa}$: 352.0061; found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$: 352.0058.

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